

Self-shaping of multicomponent drops

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ABSTRACT

In our recent study (Denkov et al., *Nature* **2015**, 528, 392-395) we showed that single-component drops, stabilized with proper surfactants, can spontaneously break symmetry and transform into various shapes during cooling. Drop self-shaping is driven by the formation of multilayers of ordered self-assembled molecules close to the drop surface, caused by a phase transition of the surfactant adsorption layer. However, most of the common substances used in industry are not pure substances, but appear as mixtures of molecules. In cosmetics, e.g. “vaseline” is a mixture of alkanes with lengths between 14 and 50 carbon atoms. Here we present a systematic study of the ability of multicomponent emulsion drops to deform upon cooling. The observed trends can be summarized as follow: (1) The general drop-shape evolution for multicomponent drops during cooling is the same as with single-component drops, however, some additional shapes are observed; (2) Preservation of the particle shape upon freezing is possible for alkane mixtures with chain length difference $\Delta n \leq 4$, for greater Δn – phase separation within droplet is observed; (3) Multicomponent particles prepared from alkanes with $\Delta n \leq 4$ plastify upon cooling due to the formation of a bulk rotator phase within the particles; (4) If a compound which cannot induce self-shaping when pure is mixed with a certain amount of a compound which induces self-shaping, then drops prepared from this mixture can also self-shape upon cooling; (5) Self-emulsification phenomena are also observed for multicomponent drops. In addition to the three recently reported mechanisms of self-emulsification (Tcholakova et al., *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, 8: 15012), a new (fourth) mechanism is observed upon freezing for alkane mixtures with $\Delta n > 4$. It involves disintegration of the particles due to a phase separation of alkanes upon freezing.

INTRODUCTION

In our recent studies,¹⁻⁴ we showed that micrometer size emulsion drops of single chemical substances such as n-alkanes, alkenes, alcohols, triglycerides etc. can change their shape upon cooling. Depending on the surfactant and oil components in the system, spontaneous transformations start at a temperature a few degrees above or below the bulk melting temperature of the emulsified oil. Subsequently drops pass through several stages in a common shape sequence – from fluid polyhedra, various flat platelets such as hexagonal, tetragonal and trigonal prisms, and finally – they transform into thin fibers. These transformations are triggered by a phase transition of the surfactant adsorption layer which causes the formation of multilayers of ordered self-assembled molecules close to the drop surface. The new self-shaping phenomenon is important in two contexts because it provides (1) new method for synthesis of particles with various complex shapes and (2) system of very simple composition which exhibits the basic processes of morphogenesis.

However, in nature (as waxes, biological membranes) as well as in consumer products that we use every day (i.e. lip sticks, cosmetic creams, etc.) alkanes are usually found as mixtures with various chain lengths. Therefore, it is of both practical and scientific interest to study the self-shaping phenomena in multicomponent emulsions.

Crystallization of alkanes and their mixtures is widely studied in the literature⁵⁻¹⁹. It is known that the odd n-alkanes with chain lengths between 13 and 41 carbon atoms (C-atoms) crystallize into a orthorhombic crystalline lattice, while the even chain length alkanes with between 14 and 26 C-atoms crystallize into a triclinic crystalline lattice.⁵ However, upon cooling, before reaching the thermodynamically stable crystalline structure, alkanes pass through intermediate phases known as rotator phases. Rotator phases are fluid phases in which molecules do have long range positional order with respect to their translational degree of freedom but the order is missing with respect to their rotational degree of freedom. Rotator phases have been observed for alkanes with chain length between 12 and 50 C-atoms in bulk⁵⁻⁸, emulsion drops⁹⁻¹¹ and microcapsules¹²⁻¹⁶.

Typically, binary alkane mixtures exhibit a single crystalline phase if the length of the longer alkane is up to 22% longer than the length of the shorter alkane in the mixture (i.e. difference in the chain length of up to 4 C-atoms for alkanes with chain length up to 20 C-

atoms).¹⁷ Otherwise, upon cooling, a phase separation within the solid phase is observed. As with the single alkanes, rotator phases have been observed as intermediate phases also for alkane mixtures. It has been shown that chain mixing increases the temperature range of stability of the rotator phases.^{12-16,18}

Mondieig et al.¹⁹ studied the phase diagrams of various binary mixtures for alkanes of consecutive chain lengths ($\Delta n = 1$) and mixtures with $\Delta n = 2$.¹⁹ Briefly, upon cooling, an alkane mixture goes from a liquid state to a two phase region where liquid and rotator phases coexist. Further cooling leads to transformation into either a rotator or a crystalline phase depending on the ratio between the alkanes in the mixtures. If a rotator phase is formed – it transforms into a stable crystalline phase at a lower temperature. A schematic phase diagram presenting the main regions observed in the binary alkane mixtures is shown in **Figure 1**. For shorter alkanes ($n \leq 20$), the rotator phase is R_I – a lamellar structure with the alkane molecules stacked perpendicularly to the lamellar planes and being able to rotate around their long axis. It has a bilayer stacking sequence ABAB.

Figure 1. General phase diagram for two component alkane mixtures.

In the current study, we present the main features of the self-shaping phenomena as observed with multicomponent drops. Consecutively we describe the processes observed upon cooling, freezing and melting of these drops and how they differ from the corresponding processes observed with single-component drops. We comment on the influence of the expanded area of stability of the rotator phases in multicomponent mixtures on the self-shaping phenomena.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

MATERIALS

As a dispersed phase in most of the emulsions studied we used mixtures of n-alkanes (abbreviated as C_n) with different chain lengths (n between 10 (decane) and 20 (eicosane)). All alkanes were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and have purity > 99%. The melting temperatures of these paraffins are between -30°C and 37°C. The alkanes were used as received.

In another series of experiments we used 1-heptadecene, 1-eicosene, 1-decanol, 1-dodecanol, 1-tetradecanol, 1,2,3-trihexadecylglyceride (tripalmitin) and pentadecylcyclohexane. We also studied emulsions prepared with commercial oil products such as cocoa butter, lard and coconut oil (purchased from a grocery store in Bulgaria, used without further purification), which are mixtures of molecules. Detailed information for the compounds and their relevant physical properties is presented in Supporting information **Tables S1** and **S2**.

As emulsifiers we used two different series of water-soluble nonionic surfactants with the commercial names Brij and Tween (all products of Sigma-Aldrich). The Brij surfactants are polyoxyethylene alkyl ethers, C_nEO_{20} , and the Tween surfactants – polyoxyethylene sorbitan monoalkylate, $C_nSorbEO_{20}$ with n varying between 16 and 18, for detailed information see Supporting information **Table S3**. All emulsifiers were used without further purification. Their concentration in the aqueous phase was fixed at 1.5 wt. %. This concentration was chosen to be sufficiently high, well above the critical micelle concentrations, to suppress drop-drop coalescence and surfactant depletion (due to adsorption on the increased surface of the deformed drops) during the experiments.

All aqueous solutions were prepared with deionized water (with resistivity > 18 M Ω ·cm) which was purified by Elix 3 module (Millipore, USA).

METHODS

Oil mixtures

The alkane mixtures were prepared by mixing two or more alkanes (in a liquid state) in a certain volume ratio. Various binary mixtures of chain lengths C_{n1} and C_{n2} with Δn between 1 (two consecutive chain length alkanes) and 10 (decane + eicosane) were studied. We also studied some ternary mixtures of alkanes and a seven-component mixture. The alkane volume ratio was varied between 10 and 90% for the longer alkane in the mixtures. Emulsions of a single alkane were also studied (i.e. volume ratio corresponding to 0 or 100% in the mixture) for comparison of the observed trends.

To check whether the same processes are observed with mixtures of compounds from different homologous series (for example alkane + alcohol or alkane + alkene etc.) we prepared various mixtures in a volume ratio 1:1. We also studied various mixtures of non-self-shaping substances (substances which cannot induce self-shaping when the emulsion drops are prepared only with them) mixed with different amounts of self-shaping substances.

Emulsion preparation

All emulsions were prepared by membrane emulsification, in which drops with relatively narrow size distribution were generated.²⁰⁻²³ The polydispersity indices of the prepared emulsions by both number and volume, σ_x , were always $\sigma_x \leq 1.1$. The polydispersity is defined as the ratio $\sigma_x = d_{x50}/d_{x84}$, where “x” is “N” (when the values are calculated by number) and “v” (by volume). The d_{x50} diameter represents the mean drop diameter, while d_{x84} represents the diameter for which 84% of the drops have drop sizes smaller than the given diameter (when calculated by number) and 84% of the dispersed oil is contained in drops with diameters smaller than the given diameter (when calculated by volume).

The oily phase was emulsified by passing it through the membrane pores under pressure, into the continuous phase (aqueous surfactant solution). We used a laboratory Microkit membrane emulsification module from Shirasu Porous Glass Technology (SPG, Miyazaki, Japan), working with tubular glass membranes of outer diameter 10 mm and working area of approx. 3 cm². We used membranes with mean pore diameter of 1, 2, 3, 5 μm and 10 μm to prepare monodisperse droplets with mean diameters around 3, 6, 10, 17 μm and 32 μm respectively.

Membrane emulsification technique was used in order to allow us to study the behavior of a large number of similar drops which are investigated under equivalent experimental conditions. In our preliminary experiments we also studied polydisperse emulsions, prepared by simple hand-shaking of the oil-surfactant mixtures. The same results were obtained with them as well.

Optical observation of the drop shape transformations.

For microscope observations, a specimen of the studied emulsion was placed in a rectangular capillary with length of 50 mm, width of 1 mm and height of 0.1 mm. The capillary was enclosed within a custom-made metal cooling chamber, with optical windows for microscope observation, see **Figure S1**. The chamber temperature was controlled by cryo-

thermostat (JULABO CF30, Cryo-Compact Circulator). The temperature in the sample during the experiment was measured using a calibrated thermo-couple probe with an accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$. The thermo-probe was inserted in one of the orifices of the aluminium thermostating chamber and mounted in the position, where a capillary with the emulsion sample would be normally placed for microscope observations. In the neighbouring orifice the actual capillary with the emulsion sample was placed. The correct measurement of the temperature was ensured by calibrating the thermo-couple with a precise mercury thermometer in the respective range of temperatures measured. Also, for single alkane experiments we always observe melting of the frozen particles at temperatures very close to T_m ($T_m \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$), where T_m is the literature reported melting temperature of the bulk oil.

All optical observations were performed with Axioplan and AxioImager.M2m microscopes (Zeiss, Germany). We used transmitted, cross-polarized white light, with included λ plate (compensator plate) situated after the sample and before the analyser, at 45° with respect to both the analyser and the polarizer. Under these conditions the liquid background and the fluid objects have typical magenta color, whereas the birefringent areas appear brighter and may have intense colors.²⁴⁻²⁵ When taking images for determination of the drop size distribution we used transmitted light. Long-focus objectives $\times 20$, $\times 50$ and $\times 100$ were used.

Freeze-thaw experiments

The freeze-thaw (F/T) experiments of the dispersed drops was performed as follows: (1) The cooling process started at a temperature which was 5 degrees higher than the bulk melting temperature of the compound with highest T_m in the studied mixture, see **Tables S1** and **S2**. The samples were cooled at a fixed cooling rate, varied between 0.15 and 1.5 K/min. The temperature in the system was lowered until complete freezing of the dispersed oil drops was observed (except for the experiment with decane where we were unable to freeze the drops entirely). Note that only the dispersed phase underwent phase transitions during our experiments and solidified. The continuous medium (aqueous surfactant solution) remained always liquid. (2) The drop melting process was performed at a fixed heating rate, 2 ± 0.3 K/min. The temperature in the system was increased until reaching the melting temperature of the longer alkane in the mixture, so all of the dispersed entities were in a liquid state.

Drop deformations

To quantify the extent of final drop deformation reached along the cooling process, we used the drop aspect ratio, defined as follows: As a reference drop size we used the diameter of the initial spherical drop. As final “drop length” we measured the longest length of the observed two-dimensional (2D) projection of the drop just before its final freezing, see **Figure S2** for illustration.

Determination of the drop size distribution in emulsions

The drop size distribution in the studied emulsions was determined from microscope images. Drop diameters were determined using two procedures. For some of the experiments we measured the diameter of the drops one by one, using custom-made image analysis software. The diameters of more than 1000 droplets were measured by this procedure. For other experiments, the drop diameter was measured using the Image Analysis Module of Axio Vision Software. More than 15,000 droplets were measured in each sample when this analysis was used. Results from the two methods were in good agreement with one another.

The mean volume-surface diameter was determined from the relation $d_{32} = \frac{\sum_i N_i d_i^3}{\sum_i N_i d_i^2}$, where N_i is the number of drops with diameter d_i .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section we present our results for drop self-shaping phenomena with mixtures and how they can be compared to the previously known observations for single compounds. First we describe the behavior of the multicomponent drops upon cooling (transformations, freezing) and then upon heating (melting). Then we discuss the self-emulsification phenomena for alkane mixtures.

Transformations upon cooling

In our recent publications¹⁻⁴, we showed that droplets from substances which exhibit rotator phase transitions self-shape into a variety of shapes upon cooling, see **Figure 2A**. This phenomenon was demonstrated for alkanes, alkenes, alcohols, triglycerides and asymmetric alkanes². It was found that no matter the substance, the droplets always follow the same evolutionary scheme – the spherical drops spontaneously change their shape, forming polyhedrons, they gradually flatten into hexagonal platelets which can evolve either into

tetragonal platelets (parallelogram) or into triangular platelets (equilateral triangle). The last stages of the evolutionary process involve growing of protrusions from the acute angles of the platelets, and also for the tetragonal ones - a capillary instability process in which the bulk of the alkane in the shaped droplet re-forms into an ellipsoidal drop with several tips from which thin fibers are extruded.

In the current study, we found that this evolutionary scheme is followed also by all droplets containing two (or more) mixed substances that we studied. Upon cooling, the multicomponent drops pass through the exact same shape evolutionary path. We did not observe any influence of the alkane chain length difference, Δn , in the mixture on the obtained non-spherical shapes upon cooling, although we varied Δn between 1 and 10 carbon atoms. Experimental pictures of multicomponent droplets with variety of shapes are shown in **Figure 2B**.

The condition for observation of the self-shaping process for multicomponent alkane drops is that the longer alkane in the mixture should be with no-more-than three C-atoms longer than the length of the hydrophobic tail of the surfactant, used to stabilize the emulsion. Shorter alkanes in the mixture could be of any length. To prove this conclusion we tested the emulsion of the binary mixture $C_{10}:C_{20} = 1:2$ (volume ratio of the alkanes in the mixture, $\Delta n = 10$), stabilized by the surfactant $C_{18}EO_{20}$. Even for this system we do observe transformations upon cooling.

Interestingly, until now we have always observed platelets with angles of 60 or 120 degrees. However, for multicomponent droplets many platelets with 90 degree angles are also formed, see **Figure 2C**. It was found that 90° angles are most often observed for mixtures of alkanes with chain length difference ≤ 4 , and for the highest cooling rate which still allows drops to self-shape.

Figure 2. Drop shape transformations observed upon cooling. (A) Main stages of the drop shape evolution, observed for single- and multicomponent droplets. **(B)** Fluid non-spherical shapes observed with multicomponent drops – $C_{14}:C_{16} = 1:1$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{16}EO_{20}$ surfactant, initial drop diameter $\approx 16 \mu\text{m}$. **(C)** Fluid shapes with 90° angles, observed with multicomponent drops ($C_{16}:C_{19} = 1:1$ v/v, $C_{18}\text{Sorb}EO_{20}$, $d_{\text{ini}} \approx 16 \mu\text{m}$, cooling rate 0.18 K/min). Scale bars, $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Drop shape evolution upon cooling is affected by the initial drop size, cooling rate, surfactant used for emulsion stabilization, and the alkane volume ratio in the mixture.

As with single component drops², we observe that smaller multicomponent drops, cooled at slower cooling rates evolve up to further stages of the evolutionary scheme upon cooling, reaching bigger aspect ratios.

| To study the effect of the alkane volume ratio in the mixture, we performed systematic experiments with various volume ratios for a mixture of tetradecane (C_{14}) and eicosane (C_{20}). We found that for a given surfactant, drops with larger amount of the shorter alkane reach further stages of the evolutionary scheme, while drops with larger amount of the longer alkane freeze at earlier stages. This effect is demonstrated in **Figure 3** for the surfactants $C_{18}EO_{20}$ and $C_{18}\text{Sorb}EO_{20}$ and drops with initial diameter $d_{\text{ini}} \approx 17 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$. As seen from **Figure 3A**, when C_{20} drops are stabilized by $C_{18}EO_{20}$ surfactant, and cooled at cooling rate 0.45 K/min , only 10 % of the drops evolve up to the platelet stage. This is easily understood, because the alkane in this case is with longer chain length than the chain length of the surfactant's tail, thus for this drops transformations are quite difficult. When into the oily phase only 20 vol. % of C_{14} alkane is added, then almost all of the drops evolve up to the platelet stage, **Figure 3B**. If the C_{14} and C_{20} alkanes are mixed in equal volume ratios, then all drops evolve reaching final stages of the evolutionary scheme, as shown in **Figure 3C**.

The type of surfactant also plays an important role in the process, as already demonstrated in our previous study². With surfactants containing a sorbitan ring as compared to ones without one in their hydrophilic head, it is more difficult induce transformations under all other equivalent conditions (slower cooling rate, smaller initial drop size, type of freezing oil). We have speculated² that the main reason for this difference is the different packing of the surfactant adsorption layer, resulting in different thickness of the rotator phases formed near the particle surface.

We observe that surfactants allowing easier transformations with single alkane, also allow easier transformations for droplets of alkane mixtures. For example, as seen in **Figure 3A**, all of the drops of $C_{14}:C_{20} = 1:1$ v/v stabilized by $C_{18}EO_{20}$ reach the final stage of the

evolutionary process, while for drops stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$ this happens only at a much greater volume ratio with respect to tetradecane, $C_{14}:C_{20} = 4:1$, **Figure 3D**.

Figure 3. Aspect ratio dependence on alkane volume ratio in the mixture. For alkane mixtures, drops containing higher percentage of the short-chain component reach bigger aspect ratio before freezing. This tendency is demonstrated for two series of emulsions stabilized by two different surfactants – $C_{18}\text{EO}_{20}$ (numbers in red) and $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$ (numbers in green). Alkane mixture $C_{14}+C_{20}$ in different volume ratios, $d_{\text{ini}} \approx 17 \pm 2\mu\text{m}$, cooling rate $\approx 0.45\text{ K/min}$. (A) Shape statistics. (B) and (C) Shapes obtained upon cooling of emulsion drops stabilized by $C_{18}\text{EO}_{20}$ surfactant, oil mixture with 20 and 66 vol. % of C_{14} respectively. (D) $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$, 80 vol. % C_{14} . Scale bars, 20 μm .

Plastification and freezing

After the drops exhibit transformations in their shape, upon further cooling they undergo a final phase transition in which fluid non-spherical particles transform into the frozen (plastified) non-spherical particles. In this section, we describe in more details the peculiarities related to this final phase transition in mixed systems.

Upon cooling of single-component drops, for compounds where shape transformations are possible, we observed² up to *three* consecutive phase transitions ($L \rightarrow R_{Cl} + L \rightarrow R_{Cv} + L \rightarrow S$). $L \rightarrow R_{Cl} + L$ occurs during the transformation from an isotropic liquid drop (L) to a non-spherical fluid particle ($R_{Cl} + L$), which may also exhibit a capillary instability, after which very thin fibers are formed ($R_{Cv} + L$), and a final phase transition when complete freezing of one of the previous states into a solid crystal is observed (S).²

However, it has been shown¹⁹ that in alkane mixtures with $\Delta n = 1-2$, below the region of the coexistence of rotator and liquid phases, there is a wide temperature range in which only rotator phase is observed prior to the formation of the stable crystalline phase, see **Figure 1** and Figures 2,3 from reference 19. Mondieig et al. report the existence of the rotator phase (before the final transition into a stable crystalline phase) down to -20 to -30°C for binary mixtures of alkanes with chain length less than 20 C atoms.¹⁹ For that reason, the expected final phase transition in our experiments with multicomponent mixture drops is $R_{Cx} + L \rightarrow R_{Cx}$ (a process of plastification) instead of to the solid phase S (crystallization), see **Figure 1**. Here, R_{Cx} denotes any rotator phase formed in the micrometer-sized drops.

For most multicomponent drops, this expected sequence of phase transformations was observed. In emulsions stabilized by C_nEO_{20} and alkanes with chain lengths similar to the number of carbon atoms in the surfactant tail, however, we observed an additional step – the extruded threads undergo a plastification phase transition before the plastification of the main body of the deformed particle, see **Figure 4** for illustration. Typically, when long threads are extruded – they are soft and flexible and easily bent. Similar threads are also observed in the initial stages of the evolutionary process of mixed $C_{14}:C_{16} = 1:1$ drops, stabilized by $C_{16}EO_{20}$ surfactant, see **Figure 4A,C**. However, when a certain temperature is reached – a phase transition only within the protrusions is observed – they suddenly become straight with some defects, seen as sharp, angular changes of thread direction, along their length, **Figure 4B,D**. After this phase transition, the fibers do not grow more or change upon further cooling which confirms that they have been plastified before the plastification of the main body of the deformed fluid particle occurs. A similar process is observed for the emulsion of $C_{16}:C_{18} = 1:1$, stabilized by the surfactant $C_{18}EO_{20}$. In this case, the temperature at which the phase transition is observed

is much closer to the temperature of plastification of the main body of the deformed particle, so the separate plastification of the fibers is not so easy to distinguish.

Figure 4. Plastification of extruded fibers. *n*-alkane mixture drops from tetradecane and hexadecane (volume ratio 1:1), stabilized by C₁₆EO₂₀ undergo a phase transition not observed with single-component drops. Upon cooling, drops change their shape and start to extrude soft and flexible protrusions (A) and (C), however at a certain temperature, below T_d but above the freezing temperature, T_f , the protrusions suddenly become straight and stiff (B) and (D). Scale bars, 20 μm .

The final phase transition, $R_{CX} + L \rightarrow R_{CX}$ (or S in the case of single-component drops), is easily detectable with an optical microscope in polarized light, because of the visible changes in the particle color. Before the final phase transition, the fluid particles do not have intense colors because the rotator phase at their periphery is with thickness around several dozens to several hundred nm.^{1,2} The colors appear when the rotator/crystalline structure is formed within the whole particle, because of the birefringence of the ordered domains of the plastified/frozen particle.

The single-component frozen particles have bright saturated colors and grained appearance which reflects their polycrystalline internal structure, see **Figure 5A**. Multicomponent plastified particles which are formed from alkanes with chain length differences up to 4 C-atoms, look very different, see **Figure 5B-D**. These particles do preserve their shape after the final freezing, but they appear much more homogeneous in structure. Also, the observed colors are very different from those observed with the single-component particles – most of the particles are almost transparent, showing bright colors only at their edges, see **Figure 5B,C**. Also, while we observe mostly green and blue colors with single-component particles, the multicomponent particles are mainly blue and yellow. **Figure 5D** shows the same particle as **Figure 5C** but with λ (compensator) plate placed at 90° with respect to the polarizer and

analyzer, instead at 45° as in the rest of the pictures (i.e. the same as in cross polarized light without compensator plate). Bright parts are observed only at the particle periphery, where the colors are in **Figure 5C**, confirming that only the molecules at the particle periphery are well ordered, while the rest of the particle is in a more disordered rotator phase.

Figure 5. Plastifying of multicomponent drops with $\Delta n \leq 4$. The alkanes are: **(A)** C_{16} **(B-E)** $C_{16}:C_{18} = 1:1$ v/v **(F)** $C_{16}:C_{17} = 1:1$ v/v. All emulsions are stabilized by the surfactant $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. **(A)** The frozen single component particles have bright intense colors and “grainy” structure. **(B)** The tetragonal bi-component particles look very different from the single-component particles. They have only faint colors and look much more homogeneous in structure. **(C,E)** Multicomponent particles have bright intense colors only at their edges, their interior is almost transparent because the particles are filled with rotator phase, rather than a crystalline phase. This hypothesis is confirmed by image **(D)** showing the same square particle as in **(C)** but with λ -plate being placed at 90° with respect to the polarizer and analyzer, instead at 45° as in all of the other pictures. **(F)** For some of the frozen particles bright, single color rods are well visible at the particle periphery. Scale bars, 20 μm .

These experimental observations are in good agreement with the phase diagrams obtained by Mondieig et al.¹⁹, according to which only rotator phases should be present at these temperatures. Thus, we speculate that the reason for the transparent parts of the particles and for their homogeneous structure, is that the final phase transition observed with multicomponent alkane drops ($\Delta n < 4$) is $R_{CX} + L \rightarrow R_{CX}$ instead to a crystalline state. The bright colors observed at the particles periphery are due to the better order of the rotator phase which has been formed

earlier during the drop shape evolution and the molecules there had more time to arrange properly. The proposed explanation is also in good agreement with the observed shrinkage upon the final phase transition, which is around 10% for the single-component particles, whereas it is around 2-3% only for these multicomponent particles.

Multicomponent drops of alkanes with chain length difference, $\Delta n > 4$, show different behavior upon cooling. They pass through several stages of the evolutionary scheme, but freezing is observed at a certain temperature. After this process, the “frozen” particles do not preserve their shape but usually shrink back to one or several spherical drops, covered with small crystallites, see **Figure 6A-C**, **Video 1** and section *Self-emulsification for multicomponent mixtures* below. This is caused by the phase separation of the alkanes within the particle. In fact, when we observe the appearance of bright colors, indicating ordering of the molecules within the particle (**Figure 6B**), this is due to the solidifying mostly of the longer-chain alkane in the mixture. Due to the big difference between the melting temperatures of the two alkanes in the mixture, the longer one solidifies while the shorter one stays in the liquid state, see **Figure 6C**. After this initial freezing, however, the rotator structure stabilizing the non-spherical shape of the particle is broken, the capillary pressure of the liquid alkane is not counter-balanced by the plastic phase any more, and the liquid fraction acquires the shape with the smallest interfacial area, i.e. – a sphere. The phase separation of alkanes with $\Delta n > 4$ within single droplet can be observed even better if higher cooling rates are used, see **Figure 6E**.

Figure 6. Freezing of multicomponent drops with $\Delta n > 4$. Fluid shapes are not preserved upon freezing. (A-C) $C_{14}:C_{20} = 1:2$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}EO_{20}$, cooling rate 0.4 K/min. (D) Schematic representation of the phase separation process – upon cooling two distinct regions are observed within the drops – a liquid part consisting mostly of the molecules of the shorter alkane and a

frozen crystal part from the longer alkane in the mixture **(E)** C14:C20 = 2:1 v/v, stabilized by C₁₈SorbEO₂₀ surfactant, cooling rate 4 K/min.. Scale bars, 20 μ m.

To preserve the shape of particles from mixtures with chain length differences greater than 4 C atoms, we can add to the binary mixture a third alkane, with an intermediate chain length. Indeed, this strategy was successful and particles from such ternary mixtures, where inter-chain length differences are less than 4 C atoms, do preserve their shapes upon freezing, see **Figure 7A,B**.

We also performed experiments with drops containing all alkanes with chain lengths between 14 and 20 carbon atoms (seven-component mixture) mixed in equal volume ratios. Interestingly, drops from this very complex mixture also self-shape, passing through the known stages of the evolutionary scheme, see **Figure 7C,D**. These particles look like the particles from binary mixtures for which $\Delta n < 4$. This experiment shows that the behavior of a multicomponent mixture is not determined by the difference between the shortest and longest components in the mixture, but rather by the greatest difference, Δn , between any two neighboring chain length components in the mixture. If it is smaller or equal to 4, then the behavior of the mixture would be as the behavior of a binary mixture with $\Delta n \leq 4$, otherwise – a phase separation in the crystalline phases will be observed upon freezing and the particles will not preserve their shape.

All these observations show that the self-shaping phenomena is present not only for single pure substances but also for various binary, ternary and even more complex alkane mixtures. Thus, providing water-soluble surfactants with long enough hydrophobic tail, the same behavior can be expected from very complex mixtures of alkanes found in the nature, for example – waxes.

Figure 7. Preservation of shape for multicomponent drops with $\Delta n > 4$. For mixtures with greatest chain length difference $\Delta n > 4$, fluid shape can be preserved after the final phase transition if a medium chain length component is added to the mixture. **(A-B)** A ternary alkane mixture $C_{14}:C_{17}:C_{20} = 1:1:1$ v/v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. **(A)** Fluid particles before plastifying. **(B)** Corresponding plastified particles. **(C-D)** A seven-component mixture from alkanes with chain lengths between 14 and 20 C atoms, mixed in 1:1:1:1:1:1:1 volume ratio. **(C)** Fluid elongated tetragonal particles. **(D)** Plastified tetragonal particles. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Self-shaping of non-alkane multicomponent drops

Here we present briefly our results for self-shaping phenomena, observed with mixtures of compounds from different homologous series.

Non-alkane compounds can be divided into two separate groups – one for the compounds which can exhibit the self-shaping phenomena by themselves² in their pure state (group 1 – triglycerides, alkyl-cyclohexanes, alkenes) and another group for the compounds which do not self-shape upon cooling (group 2).

Drops prepared from mixtures of compounds from group 1 self-shape upon cooling, passing through the known evolutionary scheme, no matter what is the volume ratio of the mixed oils, see **Figure 8A-C**. Particles prepared from them do preserve their shape upon their final phase transition, see **Figure 8A-C**.

Figure 8. Self-shaping of various multicomponent drops. Upper row – fluid particles, lower row – frozen (plastified) particles. **(A)** Hexagonal platelet obtained from mixture of 1-eicosene and pentadecylcyclohexane in volume ratio 2:1, surfactant $C_{18}\text{EO}_{20}$. **(B)** Triangular prism with protrusions obtained from mixture of pentadecylcyclohexane and 1-heptadecene in volume ratio 1:3, surfactant $C_{16}\text{EO}_{20}$. **(C)** Tetragonal prisms (one of which has a hole in the center while still fluid) obtained from mixture of heptadecane and heptadecene, volume ratio 1:1, surfactant

C₁₈SorbEO₂₀. **(D)** Hexagonal platelet obtained from mixture of 1-tetradecanol and hexadecane in volume ratio 85:15, surfactant C₁₈SorbEO₂₀. Scale bars, 20 μm .

To check the possibility for self-shaping of drops from mixtures of compounds from group 1 and group 2, we performed experiments with 1-tetradecanol mixed with hexadecane. For the stabilization of the prepared emulsions we used C₁₈EO₂₀ and C₁₈SorbEO₂₀ surfactants. Both of these surfactants do not induce shape transformations in emulsion drops prepared with pure 1-tetradecanol. However, if 1-tetradecanol is mixed with hexadecane at volume ratio up to 85 vol. % in favor of the 1-tetradecanol (C₁₄OH:C₁₆ = 85:15), then shape transformations in the emulsion drops upon cooling are observed, see **Figure 8D**.

Furthermore, to check whether mixing a self-shaping compound with non-self-shaping compound always results in the possibility for self-shaping of the drops upon cooling, we performed additional experiments with substances that are found in nature, such as the complex mixtures of molecules found in cocoa butter, lard and coconut oil. We observe drop shape transformations for all these substances if they are mixed with at least 15 vol. % alkane.

These results show the possibility for expansion of the self-shaping phenomena even beyond the many substances which self-shape in their pure state. They show that the self-shaping can be induced in many non-self-shaping substances if they are mixed with small amounts (e.g. with 15 vol. %) of a self-shaping compound.

Melting

Melting of the multicomponent particles also has some specifics as compared to the melting of those from single-components. For single-component particles we always observe melting within a very narrow fixed temperature interval ($T_m \pm 0.2\text{K}$). In contrast, multicomponent drops melt over a temperature interval, the width of which depends on Δn . The wider chain length distribution in the mixture – the wider the temperature range of melting, see **Table S3**.

The temperature range of melting is always between the melting temperatures of the pure compounds. For mixtures with $\Delta n < 4$, usually it is within 4-6 degrees and the process starts close to the bulk melting temperature of the shorter alkane, see **Figure S3**. As observed with particles prepared from C₁₆ and C₁₇ mixture, the colors of the particles disappear near the bulk melting temperature of the shorter alkane, indicating formation of a more disordered phase inside the particles. However, the non-spherical shape is preserved, showing that the melting occurs inside out. The non-spherical shape disappears only when the bulk melting temperature of the longer alkane is reached and the particle melts back into a spherical drop.

For mixtures with $\Delta n > 4$, when phase separation is observed, the temperature range of melting can be as wide as the difference between the bulk melting temperatures of the pure alkanes. For example, when mixing tetradecane and eicosane in equal volume ratio, the melting process is observed from 5°C up to 37°C. Because of the wide temperature range within which the melting process takes place, formation of some irregular non-spherical shapes without colors is observed upon heating. These irregular particles are stable over a wide temperature interval until the final melting into a spherical drop is observed.

Self-emulsification for multicomponent mixtures

The self-shaping of mixture drops to non-spherical shapes can also lead to non-equilibrium phenomena, such as self-emulsification via freeze-thaw cycles³. In this case, self-emulsification is a process in which drops significantly decrease their diameter only by cooling and heating of the sample. Three mechanisms turn out to be cooperative for the process of self-emulsification for single-component drops – repeated breakage upon cooling (mechanism 1) and fiber disintegration (mechanism 2) and crystal-melt fragmentation (mechanism 3) upon heating³. All these mechanisms are also observed for multicomponent drops.

In addition, for mixtures of alkanes with chain length difference greater than 4 carbon atoms, a fourth, very effective mechanism is observed – disintegration of the fluid shapes upon freezing, see **Figure 9** and **Video 1**. These phenomenon has the same origin as the one, described in section *Freezing* of multicomponent drops with $\Delta n > 4$. Because of the big temperature difference between the freezing temperatures of the oils, they phase separate upon freezing and mainly the long-chain component freezes in the moment of breakage. The short-chain alkane remains in the liquid state but because of the freezing of the long-chain component, the internal structure of the non-spherical particle is destroyed and spherical particles are formed due to the capillary pressure of the fluid interface.

Figure 9. Disintegration of multicomponent drops with $\Delta n > 4$ upon freezing. Fluid shapes do not preserve their shape upon freezing. **(A-B)** $C_{14}:C_{19} = 1:1$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. **(C-D)** $C_{14}:C_{20} = 2:1$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. Scale bars, 20 μm .

We performed systematic experiments to study this mechanism by varying the alkane ratio in the mixture of C₁₄ and C₂₀, with the surfactants C₁₈SorbEO₂₀ and C₁₈EO₂₀. The respective results are presented in **Figure 10A**. The most effective self-emulsification is observed for volume fraction of the shorter alkane from around 50% up to 70 vol. %.

In the emulsions stabilized by C₁₈SorbEO₂₀, for up to 40 vol. % C₁₄, mechanism three (crystal-melt fragmentation) is the most operative one. During cooling the mixed crystals formed from the platelets (see **Figure 3A** and **6C**) consist of two different types of crystal domains – one, which forms when mainly C₂₀ freezes at high temperature, and another one forming upon freezing of the C₁₄ at lower temperature. During heating, the second type of domains melt first and small liquid drops are formed from them. The crystal structure of the frozen particles is destroyed as we raise the temperature and separate crystals are formed. When the C₁₄ volume fraction is 50 vol. %, many drops evolve up to the final stages of the evolutionary scheme upon cooling, but preservation of the shape is not possible when they freeze – the particles disintegrate and form many small crystals. At this volume ratio all four mechanisms are well pronounced, making these drops with the smallest diameter after their melting, see **Video 1**. With increasing of the tetradecane volume fraction, later stages of the evolutionary process are observed, but in the final stages of the evolutionary scheme most of the oil is in one ellipsoidal drop that extrudes thin fibers. Upon freezing these ellipsoidal drops form one frozen particle which upon heating melts into a single drop. These drops have almost the same diameter as the initial drops from which they have been formed. Drop size decrease is mainly due to the fiber disintegration upon freezing (mechanism 4) but this is not too effective for the decrease of the d_{32} diameter. At 100 vol. % C₁₄, all drops easily evolve to the final stage of the evolutionary scheme and no breakages upon cooling are observed. The drop size decrease is only due to the fiber disintegration upon heating (mechanism 2).

Figure 10. Drop size decrease in multicomponent mixtures. (A) Drop size decrease for the mixture C₁₄+C₂₀ in different volume fractions, cooling rate ≈ 0.45 K/min. **(B)** Drop size decrease for emulsion drops from 50 vol. % C₁₆ and 50 vol. % other alkane. The emulsions are stabilized by the surfactant C₁₈SorbEO₂₀, cooling rate ≈ 0.45 K/min.

Size decrease for C₁₄-C₂₀ drops stabilized by the surfactant C₁₈EO₂₀ is bigger because of the easier evolution for these drops (see **Figure 3A**). At 0 vol. % C₁₄, the drops freeze in almost spherical shapes which melt back into the drops with the same size as the initial drops, i.e. no drop size decrease is observed. For up to 35 vol. % C₁₄, drop size decrease is due to the crystal-melt fragmentation process which occurs over the wide temperature interval during the melting. When the tetradecane volume fraction is above 50 vol. %, all drops easily reach the final stages of the evolutionary process. However, the difference observed between the drop size decrease the samples with 50 – 70 vol. % C₁₄ (d_{32} after one cycle ≈ 4 μm) and these with above 80 vol. % (d_{32} after one cycle ≈ 13 μm) is due to action of the newly found mechanism 4, as well as to the difference in the diameters of the fibers that are extruded from the ellipsoidal drop at the last stage of the evolutionary process. The particles in the samples with 50 – 70 vol. % C₁₄ cannot preserve their shape upon freezing, so many separate particles are formed upon the final phase transition. In these samples, fibers that are extruded are with diameter between 1 and 3.5 μm , transferring a relatively large part of the oil into the fibers. In contrast, in the samples with greater volume percentage of tetradecane, ≥ 80 vol. %, we observe extrusion of fibers with smaller diameter ($d < 0.7$ μm) which do not disintegrate upon freezing (at 100 vol. % C₁₄). The main part of the oil remains in the ellipsoidal drop which freezes and then melts back into a single drop. The drop size decrease is insignificant.

As shown in **Figure 10A**, the most effective drop size decrease after one cycle is observed when the alkanes in the mixture are in equal amounts. To study what is the dependence on the Δn in the mixture, we performed experiments with binary mixtures from 50 vol. % C₁₆ and 50 vol. % of another alkane, the chain length of which was varied between 14 and 20 C-atoms. We performed these experiments with the surfactant C₁₈SorbEO₂₀ because of the deep minimum in the drop size, observed for the mixture C₁₄:C₂₀ = 1:1. As seen in **Figure 10B**, a significant drop size decrease is observed for the mixtures of hexadecane with tetradecane and pentadecane. This is due to the extensive drop shape evolution for these mixtures – the drops easily reach the final stages of the evolutionary scheme, so mechanisms 2 and 3 are well pronounced. In the mixture C₁₆:C₁₇ = 1:1 v/v, the drop size decrease is only due to the not-very-effective (in this system) mechanism 2. However, when the longer alkane in the mixture is with

equal or longer chain length to that of the surfactant, shape transformations of the drops are less pronounced and no drop size decrease is observed within these samples.

CONCLUSIONS

More than 80 different oil mixtures were used as the oily phase to study the self-shaping phenomena in multicomponent drops. The main conclusions could be summarized as follows:

Drop self-shaping is observed for all alkane mixtures (no matter whether they are binary or with more components) whenever the longest alkane in the mixture is with no more than 3 C-atoms longer than the chain length of the surfactant hydrophobic tail. The shorter alkane could be of any length.

Self-shaping is observed also with mixtures of substances from different homologous series (e.g. alkane + alkene), if the pure compounds can self-shape upon cooling.

Transformations upon cooling can be induced also for substances which do not self-shape in their pure state, if they are mixed with substances which form drops that can self-shape upon cooling (e.g. 1-tetradecanol + alkane). The self-shaping process can be induced by adding only 15 vol. % of the self-shaping substance to the non-self-shaping one.

Multicomponent drops spontaneously transform their shape, passing through the same evolutionary scheme as single-component drops. However, with the mixtures, we also observe many regular platelets featuring 90° angles, which have not been commonly observed with single-component drops.

Binary mixture alkane drops, prepared from alkanes with chain length difference $\Delta n \leq 4$, plastify upon cooling rather than freeze. This is due to the expanded area of stability of the rotator phases, formed in alkane mixtures, as known from the literature^{14-16,18,19}. These particles preserve their non-spherical shape upon plastification. When the oil mixture and surfactant tails pack very well at the interface, it is possible to observe initial plastification of the extruded protrusions only, transforming them from soft and flexible into straight and non-flexible fibers.

Upon freezing, drops from alkanes with $\Delta n > 4$ break into several separate spherical entities because of the phase separation (freezing of one of the components only) within the drops.

The behaviour of drops with more than two alkanes is determined by the greatest difference gap Δn between consecutive chain lengths in the mixture.

Melting is observed within a temperature interval, instead at a fixed temperature (as with single-component drops). Some non-spherical colourless shapes are observed under crossed polarizers, indicating that the particle surface contains mainly the longer chain length components, while the shorter components are in the particle interior.

Upon thermal cycling, oil mixtures exhibit the self-emulsification process, reported recently for pure compounds³. In addition to the three mechanisms already described – droplets breakage upon cooling, fiber disintegration, and crystal-melt fragmentation upon heating, a fourth, new mechanism is commonly operative for mixtures. It is due to drop disintegration upon freezing for mixtures with gaps in consecutive chain lengths $\Delta n > 4$. This mechanism includes freezing of the different components at different temperatures, thus forming phase-separated crystalline domains of the longer and of the shorter components. In a binary mixture, the most efficient self-emulsification is observed when the surfactant stabilizing the emulsion is slightly longer than the longer alkane and the alkanes are mixed in equal volume amounts because all four mechanisms are most pronounced in this case.

The whole study demonstrates that the self-shaping and self-emulsification are general phenomena and can be used not only for highly pure compounds but also for sophisticated mixtures and eventually, if appropriate surfactants are chosen, even for waxes and compounds that do not self-shape in their pure state.

Supporting information:

Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

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Figure captions - Supplementary Tables, Figures and Video

Table S1. Properties of alkanes studied.

Table S2. Properties of the pure non-alkane organic phases studied.

Table S3. Properties and structural formulas of the surfactants used.

Figure S1. Experimental setup. (A) Schematic presentation of the cooling chamber, made of aluminum, with optical windows cut out, used for microscope observation of the emulsion samples. (B) The emulsions studied were contained in glass capillaries, placed in the thermostatic chamber and observed through the optical windows.

Figure S2. Definition of aspect ratio. As a measure of drop deformation we use the aspect ratio, defined as the ratio between the length of the longest line that can be drawn through the two-dimensional projection of the particle and initial drop diameter, $AR = \text{length}/d_{\text{ini}}$. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Figure S3. Melting of a multicomponent drop. Melting of multicomponent drops is observed within a narrow temperature range (when alkanes have similar chain lengths) instead at a specific temperature, as observed with single-component drops. Pictures show the melting of a $C_{16}:C_{17} = 1:1$ v/v toroidal particle, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Video 1. Disintegration of fluid shapes upon freezing for particles prepared from alkane mixtures with chain length difference, $\Delta n > 4$. Upon freezing, drops from alkanes with $\Delta n > 4$ break into several separate spherical entities due to the phase separation (freezing of the one of the components only) within drops. The video shows the process observed with drops prepared from alkane mixture $C_{14}:C_{20} = 2:1$ (volume ratio), emulsion is stabilized by the surfactant $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$.

Figure captions

Figure 1. General phase diagram for two component alkane mixtures.

Figure 2. Drop shape transformations observed upon cooling. (A) Main stages of the drop shape evolution, observed for single- and multicomponent droplets. (B) Fluid non-spherical shapes observed with multicomponent drops – $C_{14}:C_{16} = 1:1$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{16}EO_{20}$ surfactant, initial drop diameter $\approx 16 \mu\text{m}$. (C) Fluid shapes with 90° angles, observed with multicomponent drops ($C_{16}:C_{19} = 1:1$ v/v, $C_{18}\text{Sorb}EO_{20}$, $d_{\text{ini}} \approx 16 \mu\text{m}$, cooling rate 0.18 K/min). Scale bars, $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3. Aspect ratio dependence on alkane volume ratio in the mixture. For alkane mixtures, drops containing higher percentage of the short-chain component reach bigger aspect ratio before freezing. This tendency is demonstrated for two series of emulsions stabilized by two different surfactants – $C_{18}EO_{20}$ (numbers in red) and $C_{18}\text{Sorb}EO_{20}$ (numbers in green). Alkane mixture $C_{14}+C_{20}$ in different volume ratios, $d_{\text{ini}} \approx 17 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$, cooling rate $\approx 0.45 \text{ K/min}$. (A) Shape statistics. (B) and (C) Shapes obtained upon cooling of emulsion drops stabilized by $C_{18}EO_{20}$ surfactant, oil mixture with 20 and 66 vol. % of C_{14} respectively. (D) $C_{18}\text{Sorb}EO_{20}$, 80 vol. % C_{14} . Scale bars, $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 4. Plastification of extruded fibers. n-alkane mixture drops from tetradecane and hexadecane (volume ratio 1:1), stabilized by $C_{16}EO_{20}$ undergo a phase transition not observed with single-component drops. Upon cooling, drops change their shape and start to extrude soft and flexible protrusions (A) and (C), however at a certain temperature, below T_d but above the freezing temperature, T_f , the protrusions suddenly become straight and stiff (B) and (D). Scale bars, $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 5. Plastifying of multicomponent drops with $\Delta n \leq 4$. The alkanes are: (A) C_{16} (B-E) $C_{16}:C_{18} = 1:1$ v/v (F) $C_{16}:C_{17} = 1:1$ v/v. All emulsions are stabilized by the surfactant $C_{18}\text{Sorb}EO_{20}$. (A) The frozen single component particles have bright intense colors and “grainy” structure. (B) The tetragonal bi-component particles look very different from the single-component particles. They have only faint colors and look much more homogeneous in structure. (C,E) Multicomponent particles have bright intense colors only at their edges, their interior is almost transparent because the particles are filled with rotator phase, rather than a crystalline phase. This hypothesis is confirmed by image (D) showing the same square particle as in (C) but with λ -plate being placed at 90° with respect to the polarizer and analyzer, instead at 45° as in all of the other pictures. (F) For some of the frozen particles bright, single color rods are well visible at the particle periphery. Scale bars, $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 6. Freezing of multicomponent drops with $\Delta n > 4$. Fluid shapes are not preserved upon freezing. (A-C) $C_{14}:C_{20} = 1:2$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}EO_{20}$, cooling rate 0.4 K/min . (D) Schematic representation of the phase separation process – upon cooling two distinct regions are observed within the drops – a liquid part consisting mostly of the molecules of the shorter alkane and a frozen crystal part from the longer alkane in the mixture (E) $C_{14}:C_{20} = 2:1$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{Sorb}EO_{20}$ surfactant, cooling rate 4 K/min . Scale bars, $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 7. Preservation of shape for multicomponent drops with $\Delta n > 4$. For mixtures with greatest chain length difference $\Delta n > 4$, fluid shape can be preserved after the final phase transition if a medium chain length component is added to the mixture. **(A-B)** A ternary alkane mixture $C_{14}:C_{17}:C_{20} = 1:1:1$ v/v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. **(A)** Fluid particles before plastifying. **(B)** Corresponding plastified particles. **(C-D)** A seven-component mixture from alkanes with chain lengths between 14 and 20 C atoms, mixed in 1:1:1:1:1:1:1 volume ratio. **(C)** Fluid elongated tetragonal particles. **(D)** Plastified tetragonal particles. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Figure 8. Self-shaping of various multicomponent drops. Upper row – fluid particles, lower row – frozen (plastified) particles. **(A)** Hexagonal platelet obtained from mixture of 1-eicosene and pentadecylcyclohexane in volume ratio 2:1, surfactant $C_{18}\text{EO}_{20}$. **(B)** Triangular prism with protrusions obtained from mixture of pentadecylcyclohexane and 1-heptadecene in volume ratio 1:3, surfactant $C_{16}\text{EO}_{20}$. **(B)** Tetragonal prisms (one of which has a hole in the center while still fluid) obtained from mixture of heptadecane and heptadecene, volume ratio 1:1, surfactant $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. **(D)** Hexagonal platelet obtained from mixture of 1-tetradecanol and hexadecane in volume ratio 85:15, surfactant $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Figure 9. Disintegration of multicomponent drops with $\Delta n > 4$ upon freezing. Fluid shapes do not preserve their shape upon freezing. **(A-B)** $C_{14}:C_{19} = 1:1$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. **(C-D)** $C_{14}:C_{20} = 2:1$ v/v, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Figure 10. Drop size decrease in multicomponent mixtures. **(A)** Drop size decrease for the mixture $C_{14}+C_{20}$ in different volume fractions, cooling rate ≈ 0.45 K/min. **(B)** Drop size decrease for emulsion drops from 50 vol. % C_{16} and 50 vol. % other alkane. The emulsions are stabilized by the surfactant $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$, cooling rate ≈ 0.45 K/min.

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Table of Contents graphic

Supplementary information

“Self-shaping” of multi-component drops

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Table S1. Properties of alkanes studied.

	Chemical formula	Molecular weight, Mw, g/mol	Melting point, T _m , °C	Mass density, ρ, kg/m ³	Specific heat capacity, C _P , J/mol.K	Thermal conductivity, κ, W/m.K	Thermal diffusivity, χ, m ² /s
Decane	C ₁₀ H ₂₂	142.3	-30	726 (25°C)	233	0.129	1.1×10 ⁻⁷
Tetradecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198.4	5.5	759 (25°C)	438	0.141	8.4×10 ⁻⁸
Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212.4	8-10	758 (36°C)	475	0.144	8.5×10 ⁻⁸
Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226.4	18	763 (36°C)	507	0.144	8.4×10 ⁻⁸
Heptadecane	C ₁₇ H ₃₆	240.5	20-22	768 (36°C)	540	0.147	8.5×10 ⁻⁸
Octadecane	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254.5	26-29	770 (40°C)	575	0.148	8.5×10 ⁻⁸
Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268.5	30-34	772 (40°C)	609	0.142	8.1×10 ⁻⁸
Eicosane	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	282.5	37	776 (40°C)	641	0.149	8.5×10 ⁻⁸

All alkanes are purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and have purity of 99 % or higher.

Table S2. Properties of the pure non-alkane organic phases studied.

	Chemical formula	Molecular weight, Mw, g/mol	Producer	Purity	Melting point, T _m , °C	Mass density, ρ, kg/m ³	Specific heat capacity, C _P , J/mol.K	Thermal conductivity, κ, W/m.K	Thermal diffusivity, χ, m ² /s
1-decanol [1]	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ OH	158.3	Sigma Aldrich	99%	6.6	826 (25°C)	374	0.164	8.4×10 ⁻⁸
1-dodecanol [1]	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ OH	186.3	Sigma	99%	24	822 (36°C)	453	0.168	8.4×10 ⁻⁸
1-tetradecanol [1]	C ₁₄ H ₂₉ OH	214.4	Merck	> 98%	36-39	817 (48°C)	530	0.169	8.4×10 ⁻⁸
1-heptadecene [1]	C ₁₇ H ₃₄	238.5	TCI Chemicals	> 99.5%	11-11.5	783 (25°C)	513	0.150	8.9×10 ⁻⁸
1-Eicosene [1]	C ₂₀ H ₄₀	280.5	TCI Chemicals	> 97%	28.5-29	815 (36°C)	618	0.153	8.5×10 ⁻⁸
1,2,3-trihexadecylglyceride (tripalmitin)	C ₅₁ H ₉₈ O ₆	807.3	TCI Chemicals	99%	65.7	874 (70°C) [1]	1674 [1]	0.164 [2]	9.0×10 ⁻⁸
Pentadecylcyclohexane [1]	C ₂₁ H ₄₂	294.6	TCI Chemicals	≥ 98%	29	823 (30°C)	678	0.157	8.3×10 ⁻⁸

1. Website of National Institute of Standards and Technology of the United States: <http://wtt-pro.nist.gov/wtt-pro>.
2. Thomas A. Fats and Fatty Oils. Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry. **2000**. doi: 10.1002/14356007.a10_173.pub2

Table S3. Properties and structural formulas of the surfactants used.

	Non-ionic surfactant (trade name)	Number of C atoms, n	Number of EO groups, m	Producer	HLB	Structural formula
Polyoxyethylene alkyl ethers C_nEO_m	Brij 58	16	20	Sigma - Aldrich	15.7	$C_nH_{2n+1} \left[\text{O} \left(\text{CH}_2 \right)_m \text{OH} \right]$
	Brij S20	18	20		15.3	
Polyoxyethylene Sorbitan monoalkylate C_nSorbEO_m	Tween 40	16	20		15.6	
	Tween 60	18	20		14.9	

Figure S1. Experimental setup. (A) Schematic presentation of the cooling chamber, made of aluminum, with optical windows cut out, used for microscope observation of the emulsion samples. (B) The emulsions studied were contained in glass capillaries, placed in the thermostatic chamber and observed through the optical windows.

Figure S2. Definition of aspect ratio. As a measure of drop deformation we use the aspect ratio, defined as the ratio between the length of the longest line that can be drawn through the two-dimensional projection of the particle and initial drop diameter, $AR = \text{length}/d_{ini}$. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Figure S3. Melting of a multi-component drop. Melting of multi-component drops is observed within a narrow temperature range (when alkanes have similar chain lengths) instead at a specific temperature, as observed with single-component drops. Pictures show the melting of a $C_{16}:C_{17} = 1:1$ v/v toroidal particle, stabilized by $C_{18}\text{SorbEO}_{20}$. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Video 1. Disintegration of fluid shapes upon freezing for particles prepared from alkane mixtures with chain length difference, $\Delta n > 4$. Upon freezing, drops from alkanes with $\Delta n > 4$ break into several separate spherical entities due to the phase separation (freezing of the one of the components only) within drops. The video shows the process observed with drops prepared from alkane mixture $C_{14}:C_{20} = 2:1$ (volume ratio), emulsion is stabilized by the surfactant $C_{18}SorbEO_{20}$.